

The impact of music lessons in elementary school
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Annotation: This article is about music, the influence of music in elementary schools.

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Of all the types of art, it is music that most directly affects a person's perception, because it has a strong influence on the subconscious level not only on a person's feelings, but also on his mind. The music reflects the moods and experiences of a person, his emotional world. The subtlety, strength and variety of mental states revealed in music constitute its main content.

Music plays an important role in human society. Its developmental, educational and educational factors influence the formation and development of personality, its value orientations. Music as a necessary component of a person's socio-cultural life can serve as a factor of social identification, that is, express a person's belonging to a certain social group, activate a person's emotional state or contribute to his relaxation.

Given the fact that music permeates all spheres of our life, modern man is constantly in the sound space, there is an acute problem of managing the impact of the developing musical creative environment, in order to provide a musical and sound space that meets the formation of a healthy holistic creative personality.

Due to the fact that music is a developing art form (unlike painting, graphics, sculpture), it has the ability to convey a change of moods, experiences, dynamics of emotional and psychological states. Each piece of music has a kind of sensual program unfolding in time.

The outstanding Russian teacher V.A. Sukhomlinsky believed that musical education is not the education of a musician, but first of all the education of a person, that without musical education it is impossible to fully develop a child's mental development. He claimed that music is not only a great source of emotions, but also thoughts. Listening to music, the child learns about the world around him, its bright sides and colors. Musical images are born in his imagination, which reveal to the child in a new way the features of objects and phenomena of reality. The child lives in that bright world that is born under the influence of music. Therefore, the basics of musical culture, that is, the ability to perceive, feel, understand, experience a musical image, a person must certainly master from early childhood. According to Sukhomlinsky, what was missed in childhood is difficult, almost impossible to catch up in adulthood. As a rule, a person who does not love and does not understand music is a person who is not emotionally developed. He is not able to feel deeply, to understand the experiences of another.

A huge problem of our time is the low level of musical culture of our society, disinterest in the basics of classical music. As a result, schoolchildren and students are not familiar enough with classical art, museum collections, have no idea about concerts where you can hear the "live" sounds of such music. According to sociological research, the main leisure activities of Russian children and youth are computer games, watching television and listening to pop music. But the craving for pop music leads to satiety, destroys all aesthetic ideals and needs. Today, a type of person is being formed who is not capable of active, creative perception of real art, who does not experience any deep feelings. Speaking about the perception of music of academic genres by a listener without professional musical training, researchers often face a lack of understanding of this layer of culture and even its rejection. In order not to create a "gap" between real, great art and modern entertainment

music, our state should direct considerable efforts to ensure that from kindergarten to the last grade of school, children are in the hands of creatively thinking and creatively teaching teachers who are able to teach not only to love and understand music, especially classical, but also and to perceive it correctly, to understand its language.

In the upbringing of the younger generation, music is of paramount importance. In order for children to treat the world around them with kindness and empathy, they need to learn to listen and understand it from an early age, and music lessons can teach them this.

A music lesson is the main form of organizing musical education at school. And although there are still music clubs, optional classes are conducted, but a music lesson covering all children will never lose its significance. The task of the music lesson is to educate and develop aesthetic feelings, a correct idea of the beautiful, expand their knowledge, and cultivate a high artistic taste by means of musical art. Music lessons are characterized by a special emotional atmosphere, which should excite children, cause certain moods and experiences. In this process, the role of a teacher is great, who should not just love his profession and strive for improvement, but should "infect" children with love for music, instill in them a sense of beauty, convey his attitude to music not only by expressive performance of the work, but also by word, facial expressions, gestures, help children enter the world of musical images, to feel their expressiveness.

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